

PURIFICATION OF TELLURIUM BY A COMPLEX REFINING METHOD

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Kharkiv, Ukraine***Abstract**

The paper describes the study of the process of producing high-purity tellurium by a complex purification method by means of distillation in a vacuum with the use of an additional method of oxidizing refining in an ambient of inert argon gas with oxygen present in it. Thermodynamic calculations and analysis of the oxidation reactions of Te and the impurities present in it Ag, Hg, Se, Bi, Pb, S, Co, Fe, Sn, Zn during melting and filtration of tellurium under standard conditions and some of them (Pb, Zn) also during vacuum distillation have been performed. The criteria for the stability of oxide compounds of impurities were evaluated by the absolute value of the change in Gibbs free energy. The results of an experimental investigation of the complex method of refining tellurium are presented.

Keywords: tellurium, tellurium oxide, impurity oxides, oxygen potential, Gibbs free energy, tellurium purification, oxidizing refining, filtration, vacuum distillation.

Introduction

High-purity tellurium is of interest for modern materials science as an elemental semiconductor and the main component of binary and more complex semiconductors. Cadmium telluride, its solid solutions with mercury telluride are narrow-band semiconductors and are used for the manufacture of photodetectors [1], ionizing radiation detectors based on CdTe, CdZnTe, CdZnTeSe [2, 3]. At present, Cd_{1-x}Hg_xTe solid solutions are still used for the manufacture of infrared imagers. Cadmium telluride, along with zinc selenide, is considered as promising material for the manufacture of output windows of powerful CO₂ lasers [4], and along with silicon, it is a prospective material for the development of advanced technologies in solar power engineering, and is used for the manufacture of so-called thin-film elements. Thin-film photovoltaic modules made of CdTe distinguish by good UV radiation absorption features (up to 90%) compared to silicon, as well as by inexpensive and fast production. Such a thin-film technique provides serious grounds for unprecedented technological progress in alternative energy. Other tellurides include, in particular, cadmium manganese telluride CdMnTe. It belongs to the class of complex chalcogenides and is a well-known magnetic semiconductor, which is commonly used to control the polarization of radiation by a magnetic field in Faraday cells, as well as for the manufacture of solar cells and infrared sensors [5]. Solid solutions based on bismuth telluride turned out to be effective materials for thermal to electrical energy converters [6].

The review [7] provides a systematization of data on methods of fine cleaning of tellurium and on identification and analysis of factors that determine the possibilities of certain methods of obtaining high-purity

tellurium. The performance capabilities of tellurium ultrapurification techniques in the form of a simple substance as well as methods based on the separation of tellurium from its high clean compounds are considered. Data on the content of impurities in tellurium purified by various methods are given. In the purest tellurium samples, the concentration of metal impurities does not exceed 10⁻⁶ - 10⁻⁷ mass %. The content of gas-forming impurities and analogous elements is higher and found in the range of 10⁻³ - 10⁻⁵ mass %.

1. Urgency of the problem and formulation of the task

There are data [8, 9] that the melting of tellurium is accompanied by a decrease in the content of some impurities, especially aluminum, silicon, magnesium, and a copper also when special fluxes are used. In [10-12], the research was carried out to study the possibility of using oxidizing fusing as a method of tellurium purification. The main reaction of oxidizing refining, considered in these papers, is the interaction of impurities with tellurium dioxide:

With taking into account the fact that the activity of tellurium in molten tellurium and the activity of tellurium dioxide in slag can be taken as equal to one, the equilibrium constant for this reaction has the form:

$$K = \frac{a_{Me_nO_m}}{a_{Me}^n}, \quad (2)$$

where $a_{Me_nO_m}$ is the activity of impurity metal oxides in slag, a_{Me} is the activity of impurity metal in molten tellurium.

The greater value of K, the easier the impurity should be removed during oxidizing refining of tellurium. The calculated values of K are given in [10].

Al, Si, Sb, As and Mg, the K has large values, should be removed most easily during melting in the absence of interaction of these elements with tellurium and their oxides – with other slag oxides. Fe, Co, Zn, S, Hg, Sn can also be oxidized full enough. Se and Ag will be concentrated in molten tellurium. The behavior of Bi, Pb and Cu, for those the values of K are within the range of $10^1 - 10^4$, needs clarification.

As the research have shown, the use of ammonium nitrate as an oxidizing agent can significantly reduce the content of Al, Sb, Fe, Zn and Na. Selenium which does not oxidize, during refining can be removed into the gas phase in a hydrogen atmosphere [7], but impurities of the second group are not removed under these conditions.

Thus, when melting is performed in the optimal mode (temperature 750-800 °C, settling time 0.5-1.0 h, additive of 5% ammonium nitrate and 5% phosphorus pentoxide, a crucible made of inert material), the ultrapurification of tellurium is achieved by removing of impurities present in it.

Oxidizing fusion of technical tellurium in the presence of impurities in the form of elements or tellurides is described by reaction (1) and by the following (3) and (4):

This paper describes a melting installation that combines the melting of tellurium and its fine filtration in single apparatus made of inert material. The analysis of the composition of molten tellurium showed that after improved melting due to the filtration of the melt from the smelter, additional reducing of content of lead, silicon, sulfur and iron is achieved by 3-9 times, and of sodium and aluminum by 40-100 times, compared to the composition of the original powder tellurium. Additional refining of molten tellurium is achieved due to the further distillation process.

One of the options for oxidizing refining of tellurium is distillation in a stream of superheated water vapor [13].

The influence of availability of tellurium oxide on the tellurium purification degree of impurities in the distillation process was considered in [14]. It was established that the presence of tellurium oxide which is a collector of impurities, leads to a significant increase in the cleaning degree. This conclusion is confirmed by model experiments when introducing tellurium oxide in the amount of 0.10-0.12% of the starting substance G_0 loading.

It should be noted that the presence of oxide reduces the rate of tellurium evaporation by 2-3 times. Another negative technological factor is the interaction of oxide with quartz, that leads to a rather rapid destruction of the equipment.

Thus, the above analysis of literature data shows that for additional purification of tellurium, oxidation reactions of impurities and their oxides with additives of tellurium oxide or other special oxidizers are considered. It is interesting to consider the formation of oxide films on the surface of molten metal both in an inert gas

atmosphere and in a vacuum as a result of the chemical reaction of residual oxygen in the surrounding ambience with atoms of the base metal and atoms of impurity elements. To do this, it is necessary to have the value of the energy of the impurities oxides formation at various temperatures and magnitudes of the oxygen partial pressure. Such calculations are given below.

Taking into account the above, the goal of this work is to study the process of obtaining high-purity tellurium by a complex distillation method with the use of an additional method of oxidizing refining in an atmosphere of inert argon gas with the oxygen present in it.

2. Thermodynamic analysis of impurities oxidation reactions during melting and filtration of tellurium

The impurities of nickel, lead, magnesium, iron, cobalt, zinc, mercury, tin, aluminum, silicon, antimony, sulfur, bismuth, copper, silver, selenium present in tellurium can be removed from Te in the form of their oxides NiO, PbO, MgO, FeO, CoO, ZnO, HgO, SnO, Al₂O₃, SiO₂, SbO₂, SO₂, Bi₂O₃, Cu₂O, Ag₂O, SeO₂. Such removal of impurities can be carried out by the method of oxidizing melting of tellurium which, in turn, forms with oxygen a stable oxide TeO₂. The removal of metal impurities from tellurium in the form of oxides takes place under the condition that these oxides are more stable compared to the stability of TeO₂ in certain ranges of changes in temperature and pressure of the surrounding gas environment. The basic reaction of oxidizing refining is described by equation (1).

In this way, impurities replace tellurium in tellurium oxide with the release of pure tellurium, that is, with its purification. The reaction equilibrium constant is of the form: $K = \frac{a_{\text{Me}_n\text{O}_m}^{2/m} \cdot a_{\text{Te}}}{a_{\text{Me}}^{2n/m} \cdot a_{\text{TeO}_2}}$, where a_{TeO_2} and $a_{\text{Me}_n\text{O}_m}$ – the activities of tellurium oxides and impurity oxides, respectively; a_{Te} , a_{Me} – the activities of tellurium and metal impurities in tellurium.

The magnitude of the strengths of oxidative compounds can be estimated by the value of the oxygen potential or by the absolute value of the decrease in the Gibbs free energy $|\Delta G_{\text{MeO}}|$. The value of $|\Delta G_{\text{MeO}}|$ is directly affected by the temperature and pressure of the surrounding gas environment. One of the most common characteristics of Me_nO_m stability is the standard change in Gibbs energy ΔG° at the formation of impurity oxides according to reaction:

Let's consider divalent metals-impurities the reaction of the formation of oxides is of the form:

In this case when the metal and oxide are pure phases and do not form solutions, the constant of reaction (6) is of the form: $K_p = \frac{1}{(P_{\text{O}_2})_{\text{MeO}}}$, where P_{O_2} is the equilibrium oxygen pressure which the standard energy change ΔG° is related by the ratio to:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_p = -RT \ln \frac{1}{(P_{\text{O}_2})_{\text{MeO}}} = RT \ln (P_{\text{O}_2})_{\text{MeO}}, \quad (7)$$

where T is temperature, °K; R is a universal gas constant.

Let's first consider the interaction of oxygen with tellurium itself. Tellurium with oxygen forms two oxides: TeO_2 ($T_{\text{melt}} = 1006 \text{ K}$) i TeO_3 ($T_{\text{melt}} = 673 \text{ K}$) [15], and TeO_2 is more stable. The change in the Gibbs potential at temperatures below the boiling point of tellu-

rium in the range of $790 < T < 990 \text{ °K}$ is shown in Figure 1. It can be affirmed that at relatively low temperatures (778...903 °K), below the boiling point of tellurium T_{boil} , evaporation of Te in the form of TeO_2 can occur (see table 106 in [16]).

Figure 1. Change in Gibbs free energy during the formation of TeO_2 at $T < T_{\text{boil}}(\text{Te})$

Now we will consider the change in the Gibbs potential during the formation of impurity oxides in Te and TeO_2 under standard conditions: at the atmospheric pressure and the temperature of 298 °K which will then be extended to larger values. Such dependences of the change in ΔG_{MeO} are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. There you can see the almost complete consistency of the specified dependences with the results obtained in [10–12] where the decimal logarithms of the constants K for the metal oxides formation reactions are presented. So, impurities Mg, Al, Si, Sb, As (see Figure 2), as well as Zn, Fe, Sn, Co, S (Figure 3) have large values of the decrease in the Gibbs potential $\Delta G_{\text{(MeO)}}$ during the formation of oxides of these impurities. Moreover, the absolute magnitudes of their $\Delta G_{\text{(MeO)}}$ significantly exceed $|\Delta G_{\text{(TeO}_2\text{)}}|$. Therefore, these impurities must be completely oxidized and removed from the tellurium matrix in the process of oxidizing refining. On the other

hand, Se_2O , Ag_2O oxides have the corresponding $|\Delta G|$ values smaller than $|\Delta G_{\text{(TeO}_2\text{)}}|$ or close (Cu_2O) to it, so they should accumulate in the tellurium melt. As for Bi and Pb, the potential change $|\Delta G|$ during the formation of their oxides is fairly close to $|\Delta G_{\text{(TeO}_2\text{)}}|$, although slightly larger, so their behavior remains uncertain. It should be noted that we have only one discrepancy with the results of paper [10] where it was shown that the decimal logarithm of the reaction constant K of HgO formation has a value of $\sim 6-7$, that is close to $\lg(K)$ for the reaction of SnO formation. Therefore, according to the results of [10], mercury should be oxidized quite completely. At the same time, Figure 2 shows that $|\Delta G_{\text{(HgO)}}|$ is much smaller than $|\Delta G_{\text{(TeO}_2\text{)}}|$, therefore mercury oxide is either not formed in molten tellurium at all or when formed it decomposes at $T > 750 \text{ °K}$.

Figure 2. Changes in the Gibbs potential during the formation of TeO_2 , as well as oxides of impurities As, Sb, Si, Al, Mg in tellurium under standard conditions.

Figure 3. Changes in the Gibbs potential during the formation of TeO_2 , as well as oxides of impurities Ag, Hg, Se, Bi, Pb, S, Co, Fe, Sn, Zn in tellurium under standard conditions.

Since the tellurium distillation process was carried out in a vacuum, it is of interest to evaluate the effect of vacuum on the formation and stability of oxides. For such an estimate, you can use the standard change in Gibbs energy ΔG_{MeO}^0 , corrected for the amount that takes into account the transition of the metal to the gaseous state. For the case when the activity of MeO is equal to 1 and the boiling temperature of the metal $T_{\text{boil}}^{\text{Me}}$ is lower than the boiling temperature of the oxide $T_{\text{boil}}^{\text{MeO}}$, the oxygen potential of formation, for example, a divalent metal oxide, can be found using the formula [15]:

$$\Delta G_{\text{MeO}} = \Delta G_{\text{MeO}}^0 - 2RT \ln \frac{P}{1.03 \cdot 10^5}, \quad (8)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is temperature, K; P – metal vapors pressure, Pa.

If $T_{\text{boil}}^{\text{Me}} > T_{\text{boil}}^{\text{MeO}}$, then formula (8) should be rewritten as:

$$\Delta G_{\text{MeO}} = \Delta G_{\text{MeO}}^0 + 2RT \ln \frac{P}{1.03 \cdot 10^5}. \quad (9)$$

We will demonstrate the dependence of $\Delta G(P, T)$ using the example of the formation of oxides of zinc

and lead impurities. The change in $\Delta G(\text{ZnO})$ during zinc oxide formation depending on temperature and pressure is shown in Figure 4. We can see from the figure that with increasing temperature, the stability of zinc oxide decreases. Figure 4a shows the change in ΔG during the formation of oxide in the condensed, i.e., solid and liquid state of zinc, as well as in the solid state of ZnO. Zinc evaporates intensively at the temperature $T = 1180$ °K and under atmospheric pressure. The effect of vacuum on the Gibbs free energy value is displayed in Figure 4b which shows that as the vacuum level increases the stability of ZnO decreases. Thus, the oxide decomposes already in the vacuum of 0.00133 Pa (10^{-5} torr) at $T > 1380$ °K. The studied interval in Figure 4b is limited by the maximum temperature of 1500 °K. Since vacuum distillation can be carried out at temperatures of $0.6 T_{\text{boil}}$ [17], the linear dependences of Figure 4b can probably be approximated to the low-temperature region down to ~ 710 °K at the low pressure of 10^{-4} – 10^{-5} torr (0.0133–0.00133 Pa).

Figure 4. Change in Gibbs free energy per mole of O_2 during the formation of ZnO within the temperature ranges: a) 298 – 1179,35 K (standard change of ΔG_{ZnO}° in the condensed state and under atmospheric pressure); b) 1180 – 1500 K. The dependences of Figure 4b were calculated according to (8).

Three lead oxides are known in the condensed state: PbO_2 , Pb_3O_4 , PbO , and the first two are unstable and decompose to form PbO [16]. Therefore, the removal of the lead impurity from the matrix of tellurium takes place in the form of a PbO compound. The behavior of the Gibbs free energy during the formation of a

stable PbO oxide in a wide temperature range is shown in Figure 5. Since in the Pb – O system the boiling point of Pb is higher than that of PbO , the curves in Figure 5b were calculated according to formula (9).

Figure 5. Change in the Gibbs thermodynamic potential per mole of oxygen at the formation of PbO : a) in the condensed state of lead; b) during evaporation of Pb in the process of vacuum distillation.

Figure 5b shows that as the vacuum level increases, the $|\Delta G|$ and stability of lead monoxide rise and, thus, the probability of lead removal from the tellurium matrix increases during oxidizing refining.

With regard to the influence of vacuum on the formation of oxides of other impurities, it should be noted that the changes in the Gibbs potential for Al_2O_3 , Bi_2O_3 , CoO , FeO , HgO , MgO , NiO , SeO_2 were calculated by the formula (8) with correction for the coefficients in the corresponding equations and recount per mole oxygen. At the same time, the appearance of curves of the graphs $\Delta G_{(MexOy)}$ depending on P, T was qualitatively similar to those in Figure 4b. On the other hand, $\Delta G_{(MexOy)}$ depending on P, T for Ag_2O , Cu_2O , Sb_2O_3 , SiO_2 , SO_2 , As_2O_3 , SnO was calculated with corre-

sponding corrections according to formula (9). The appearance of the obtained curves was qualitatively similar to those of Figs. 5b. Detailed information about the thermodynamics of the formation of these impurities oxides will be presented in the next paper.

Thus, the performed analysis shows that impurities Zn, Sn, Fe, Co, Bi, S, Pb, Cu for which the change in the Gibbs potential modulus at the oxides formation is greater than $|\Delta G_{(TeO_2)}|$, will form oxides, replacing tellurium in TeO_2 . These oxides are then removed by filtering the molten tellurium.

The impurities Se, Hg, Ag, having the Gibbs potential for the creation of their oxides by an absolute magnitude smaller than $|\Delta G_{(TeO_2)}|$ at the TeO_2 formation, will enter the tellurium melt, releasing oxygen for the formation of oxides of tellurium and impurities

present in it. Selenium and mercury, according to their separation coefficients, are removed at the stage of removal of volatile impurities, and silver remains in the residue in the crucible during the distillation process.

3. Tellurium purification process by a complex method

As a result of the analysis of literature data on the use of distillation methods for refining tellurium, the fact takes a notice that most of them are performed according to a simple one-time or multiple distillation scheme with a small yield (30...60%) of a suitable prod-

uct. At the same time, the inventory of impurity elements in tellurium contains volatile and non-volatile impurities (see Table 1). Impurities that located in the table above the row with Te are classified as volatile, and those below Te are classified as non-volatile. Therefore, simple distillation will not provide optimal conditions for refining tellurium due to the transfer of volatile impurities into the condensate. In this regard, the processes of removing volatile and non-volatile impurities must be separated and carried out continuously in single refining cycle.

Table 1

Calculated values of ideal impurity separation coefficients α_i during molecular distillation of tellurium in vacuum

Composition of steam molecules	Temperature, K			
	700	800	900	1000
P ₄	$9,6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-
S	$7,0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-	-	-
Fr	$1,2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5,6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-	-
Cs	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3,1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2,2 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
Rb	$5,2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3,7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-
Se	$6,1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1,9 \cdot 10^2$	-
K	$6,8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,9 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3,4 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5,2 \cdot 10^{-2}$
As ₄	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1,7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-	-
Cd	$3,3 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5,9 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7,8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9,2 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Zn	$3,4 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$4,2 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$4,1 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3,8 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Te	1	1	1	1
Na ₂	2,7	2,8	2,5	2,2
Mg	5,3	3,9	2,5	1,9
Li	$7,4 \cdot 10^1$	$4,2 \cdot 10^1$	$2,4 \cdot 10^1$	$1,5 \cdot 10^1$
Sr	$2,6 \cdot 10^2$	$1,4 \cdot 10^2$	$7,1 \cdot 10^1$	$1,0 \cdot 10^1$
Ra	$7,9 \cdot 10^2$	$4,4 \cdot 10^2$	$2,4 \cdot 10^2$	$1,5 \cdot 10^2$
Sb	$7,0 \cdot 10^2$	$1,8 \cdot 10^2$	$5,6 \cdot 10^2$	$5,7 \cdot 10^2$
Ca	$1,3 \cdot 10^3$	$5,6 \cdot 10^2$	$4,8 \cdot 10^2$	$1,8 \cdot 10^2$
Tl	$4,5 \cdot 10^3$	$1,8 \cdot 10^3$	$7,8 \cdot 10^2$	$3,7 \cdot 10^2$
Ba	$4,9 \cdot 10^3$	$2,1 \cdot 10^3$	$9,0 \cdot 10^2$	$4,5 \cdot 10^2$
Pb	$1,5 \cdot 10^5$	$4,3 \cdot 10^4$	$1,4 \cdot 10^4$	$5,2 \cdot 10^3$
In	$8,6 \cdot 10^7$	$1,0 \cdot 10^7$	$1,5 \cdot 10^6$	$3,2 \cdot 10^5$

During the melting of refined tellurium, surface impurities in the form of oxides, suboxides and metal compounds, both based on Te and impurity elements, whose volatility may differ from that of the pure component, accumulate on the surface of the melt mirror. The presence of surface impurities leads to: a) the transfer of volatile components of the oxide film into the distillate and b) a significant decrease in the productivity of the refining process and in the yield of a suitable product.

Removal of the oxide film and slags from the surface of the melt during the tellurium distillation is an

important moment in increasing the efficiency of ultrapurification. One of the technological methods for removing oxide pollution can be liquid metal filtration. In this regard, the task of research of the complex process of Te distillation proposed in this paper was set, that allows for step-by-step removal of volatile impurities from tellurium with filtration (by an element of oxidizing refining) and further removal of non-volatile impurities by distilling of the main element on a condenser.

To implement the step-by-step Te purification process, the distillation installation was proposed, and its design is schematically shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Scheme of the installation for refining (a – filtration, b – distillation):

1 – camera, 2 – condenser, 3 – additional crucible, 4 – heater, 5 – basic crucible, 6 – support, 7 – Te filtrate; 8 – source tellurium, 9 – film of non-volatile oxides and slags, 10 – volatile impurities, 11 – non-volatile impurities, 12 – Te distillate.

The installation contains a vacuum chamber 1, where a heater 4 and a crucible 5 are placed. At the filtration stage (Figure 6a), in the upper part of the quartz crucible 5, an additional crucible 3 of the same shape with a hole in the middle and with the original tellurium 8 was placed. The additional crucible was covered with condenser 2. Te flows through the hole into the crucible 5 at a temperature above the melting point. At the same time, volatile impurities are evaporated on the condenser 2, and non-volatile oxides and slags are retained on the rounded surface of the additional crucible 3 in the form of a film 9. During filtration, cleaning occurs due to: 1) evaporation and condensation of volatile impurities (K, As, Se, Rb, Cs, S, P, Hg, etc.) on the condenser 2; 2) removal of oxides and slags enriched with impurity elements 9. As shown by the analyses of the impurity composition of tellurium poured into the crucible, the content of separate volatile impurities in it decreases by more than 10 times.

In this case, in addition to the oxidation of impurity elements on the surface of molten tellurium, the Te oxide film sorbs impurity elements and their oxides. The basic principle is that the oxide part of the main element (AO), where A represents Te, extracts impurity from the liquid phase in the form of an oxide B_rO_s , where B is an impurity element, r and s are the indices indicating the ratios of the corresponding valences. Impurities in the form of B_i ($i = 1...m$) and $(B_rO_s)_j$ ($j = 1...n$) are retained in the oxide phase of the base metal. The reaction is of the form $sAO + rB \leftrightarrow B_rO_s + sA$ at

equilibrium. Thus, filtration in this case is an additional element of cleaning. The filtration process was carried out in an atmosphere of inert gas argon of technical purity under the pressure in the chamber ~ 1 atm with a volume fraction of oxygen in it of 0.002%.

After draining the metal into the crucible 5, temperature was lowered, and the condenser 2 along with additional crucible 3 was replaced by another clean condenser (Figure 6b). Then the metal was cleaned of non-volatile impurity elements by distilling of the base on this condenser with a fraction of distillation up to 95%. The tellurium distillation process was carried out in a vacuum under the chamber pressure of no more than 10^{-1} Pa at the evaporation temperature $T_{\text{evap}} = T_{\text{melt}} + (50...60)^\circ\text{K}$ and the condensation temperature $T_k = T_{\text{melt}} - (40...50)^\circ\text{K}$, where T_{evap} , T_{melt} and T_k – evaporation, melting and condensation temperatures, respectively. $T_{\text{melt}} = 722,7^\circ\text{K}$.

During the tellurium refining process, crucibles and condensers made of high-purity fused quartz were used, that are applied in the electronic industry to grow single crystals of semiconductors Si, GaAs, and others.

The Table 2 shows the chemical composition of the source tellurium and its distillate, produced during step-by-step distillation of volatile impurities with filtration and subsequent removal of non-volatile impurities by vacuum distillation.

The elemental composition of tellurium before and after refining was monitored by a mass spectrometer using laser mass spectrometry.

Table 2

The content of the main impurities in the source tellurium, after its heating, filtration and distillation in a vacuum (distillate)

Impurity	Grade, product		
	T00 (analysis)	after filtration	distillate
	impurity 10 ⁵ mas. %, no more		
Se	700	600	10
Pb	90	30	4
Cu	200	60	0,6
S	600	150	20
Na	500	200	0,2
Si	80	50	1
Al	120	20	2
Fe	70	7	0,4
As	300	200	18
Sn	400	100	1
Sb	500	350	2
Ni	100	50	0,5
Te, %	99,96	99,98	99,9995

The analysis of the obtained results shows that the one-time distillation in a vacuum with step-by-step distillation of volatile and non-volatile impurities with filtration of oxides secures almost 100-fold purification of Te in terms of the total content of impurities.

Conclusions

Literature data on oxidizing refining of tellurium are analyzed. The efficiency of the process of oxidizing refining of Te with an addition of tellurium oxide or other special oxidizing agents was investigated.

The thermodynamics of oxidation reactions were calculated and the behavior of impurities during melting and filtration of tellurium was analyzed. It has been shown that the impurities present in tellurium, when it melts in an atmosphere of an inert gas with an oxygen available there, will form their own oxides (Zn, Sn, Fe, Co, Bi, S, Pb, Cu), or be released from oxides into the melt (Se, Hg, Ag) which are then removed by filtration and step-by-step cleaning of volatile and non-volatile impurities.

Experimental studies of complex refining of tellurium were performed. The studies have shown that single distillation in vacuum with step-by-step distillation of volatile and non-volatile impurities with filtration of oxides secures purification of tellurium by almost two orders of magnitude.

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